

Empowering students as game designers: a case study on triangle classification

Type of contribution: Research Report

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Keywords: Game-based learning, classification, secondary education, empirical study.

Introduction

High school mathematics education has seen a rise in the adoption of game-based learning methods, which engage students and promote a deeper understanding of complex concepts while enhancing their motivation and creativity (Sharma et al., 2022). In the realm of education, the intersection of digital tools and game design has ushered in a transformative paradigm where learners transit seamlessly from players to designers. This shift not only empowers students to engage with a diverse array of affordances for constructing and remixing games but also encourages critical analysis of game mechanics and identification of areas for improvement (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2023). A key aspect which allows this exploration revolves around the concept of a “black-and-white” game system (Kynigos, 2008). This framework blends structured elements with open-ended possibilities, offering learners pre-designed game elements, akin to black box artefacts, yet encouraging them to delve into customization and modification (white box). In this way, learners are empowered to engage in iterative design processes, fostering creativity and critical thinking while promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing.

With the study here presented, we will investigate how high school students can turn into game designers by means of a gameplay system, SorBET, which allows one to create a customized classification game. If other empirical studies have focused on the potentialities of learning through modding predesigned games (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2023), the specificity of this study lies in the exploration of designing a game as learning process. Designing a game should be intended as a step-by-step process that reflects those phases typical of the prototyping process (Simon & Cox, 2019): *analysis of users’ needs, design and development of a prototype, feedback and evaluation of the prototype*. Such phases are usually repeated iteratively until reaching a satisfactory result. The research question leading our investigations can be formulated as: *How can the process of designing a game support students’ mathematical thinking and understanding of an explored mathematical topic?* The preliminary analysis of a learning experiment on triangle properties will help us to shed light on this issue. This paper represents only a snapshot of our ongoing exploration, offering insights into the unfolding narrative of learners as game designers and the transformative potential inherent in their journey.

SorBET - a classification authoring tool

SorBET (Sorting Based on Educational Technology)¹ is an online constructionist authoring system developed by the Educational Technology Laboratory of the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. Its purpose is to operate as a “game generator”, assisting teachers and students with no prior programming expertise in playing, modifying, but also creating their own classification games (Grizioti & Kynigos 2023; Grizioti & Nikolaou, 2023). The rationale behind SorBET gameplay is based on the process of quick decision-making regarding the classification of objects falling at a constant rate, into the appropriate category. Users, as designers, can modify or design from scratch elements of the game, such as the objects to be dropped and the number of times each will appear during the game, as well as the featured categories and the relation between them. The classification model employed does not adhere strictly to a one-to-one relationship; rather, it allows objects to be assigned to multiple categories, resulting in a one-to-many categorization (Nikolaou, 2022). Consequently, there may be instances of overlap or exclusion among established categories, prompting discussion among participants (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2023) and, potentially, aiding in the development of skills to predict and identify attributes and generate knowledge they have not yet encountered. Learners can also set the speed and density of the falling objects (Nikolaou, 2022).

Method

The learners involved in this study are 20 9th graders from an Italian high school class. The experimental plan has been designed by the researchers and the teacher according to the three phases of the prototyping process. Such an experiment was meant to give students the possibility to use their already possessed knowledge on triangles classification (by sides, by angles, and auxiliary elements), and revise and consolidate it throughout the designing process. Students had learnt about triangles during their middle school formation and had consolidated it with some frontal lectures before starting the experiment. Students received a message from a middle school teacher asking for them to design a game for her 7th graders (*analysis of users' needs*). In the first lesson (two hours), students were introduced to SorBET and its functionalities. Divided into five groups, they were invited to play with some online example games to become familiar with the tool and explore its editing interface. Indeed, such online example games are “half-baked” (Kynigos, 2008), meaning that they are incomplete or contain “bugs” on purpose to challenge users and prompt them to reflect on what is right and wrong, involving them in a redesign process according to their personal understandings. After this playing phase, students were requested to plan the design of their own game and collect notes and ideas on a worksheet (*design*). During the second lesson (two hours), the five groups developed their own games (*development*), and answered some questions to reflect on their elaborated design. As individual homework, each student reviewed two games according to eight questions focused on the categories, mathematical features of the chosen objects, one-to-many correspondence, and gaming aspects (*feedback and evaluation*). These answers were collected in a Padlet. The third lesson started with a collective teacher-led discussion focused on analyzing key student responses and identifying areas for improvement (*feedback and evaluation*). Moreover, some technical hints were shared to support

¹ <http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/sorbet/>

students in exploiting at best SorBET functionalities. After one hour of discussion, students, divided into the same groups, spent the rest of the lesson redesigning their games in light of their peers' feedback and the insights from the discussion (*design and development*). The experimental sequence concluded with a one-hour lesson during which students wrote an open-ended report. The assignment requested students to outline three aspects: the design of their game and how it evolved, how the feedback from their peers and the teacher was integrated into the game, and how the game-designing process influenced their understanding of the explored mathematical topic. Throughout the experiment, we collected several pieces of data: the five groups' games (initial and final), their answers to the design questions, peer reviews on Padlet, researchers' notes from the collective discussion, and students' final reports. To answer our research question, we analysed qualitatively the collected material: the initial and final versions of the games were compared, and the identified changes were related to the feedback received by their peers and during the discussion. Our interpretations were integrated with the reflections elaborated by the learner-designers themselves in their reports.

Results

Our interpretative process led us to identify four main aspects which undergo some changes and so are worthy to be analyzed: classification, mathematical elements, gaming, and engagement. In what follows we will elaborate on them by referring to some examples.

Classification: The five groups adopted several boxes (from seven up to 10) in the first version of their games mixing up different classifications. Even though in several posts on Padlet, students acknowledged that “the boxes of the game refer to more than one classification”, it was the feedback received by the teacher during the discussion that led the groups to focus only on one classification (by sides, by angles, auxiliary elements) in the second versions of their games. Games that referred to the same classification showed elements of differences: for instance, the game “Triangles for everyone” has as categories rectangles, acutangles, obtusangles, while “All friends of the angles” in addition to those three also included equiangular and degenerate. From the peers' feedback on Padlet, it also emerged that the one-to-many correspondence was not used accurately. Student B. noticed that in “Triangleland”, “All angles of 60° ” was inserted only in equilateral, but had to be inserted also in acutangle”. Such correspondence was exploited by the groups more subtly (objects were set to fall more than once and all the possible boxes were ticked correctly in most cases).

Mathematical elements: if on Padlet some students declared that in some cases they were not able to classify the falling objects because they were not clear enough: in revising their games, the groups paid attention to highlighting relevant mathematical elements of the triangles (e.g., equal sides with some equal ticks). Moreover, a wide range of mathematical properties can be observed in the final versions of the games which were not used before: “Trianglemania” introduced the object “the sum of internal angles is 180° ” as an element that fits all boxes and was reproduced as many times as the available categories or the object “2 angles of 45° ” was used to denote a rectangle triangle in “All friends of the angles”. The introduction of these properties could also be interpreted as an expression of creativity (Sharma et al., 2022).

Gaming: In the revised versions of the games, students paid more attention to SorBET gaming aspects such as falling objects and their representations. An element of novelty that can be noticed in the

revised versions was the introduction of real objects exemplifying different kinds of triangles (e.g., a road sign as an equilateral triangle as in Trianglemania), a hint that was shared during the collective discussion and that was implemented by three groups. Sometimes also mistakenly (two groups used the picture of a cone to exemplify an isosceles triangle). Moreover, student N. observed that when using texts as objects “we focused on the simplicity of words to make them even more understandable”.

Engagement: Reflecting on the whole activity, student R. wrote that after their peers’ feedback “we changed the game (in a positive sense): we decreased the elements, making them clearer and more interesting”. Student E. concluded that the good side of the project was “to be useful to others (as in this case) and to learn even boring concepts in an alternative way”.

Final remarks

Although in some games there are still aspects to be agreed upon, the perspective of engaging students as active participants in their own learning journey holds promise for transforming traditional mathematics education. In student H.’s words “designing and commenting a game means knowing even more than what you write; in order to be able to give a judgement to the work of others, you need to know very well the topics”. This awareness seems to be a valuable achievement in the end.

Acknowledgements

This study is funded by the HORIZON-WIDERA project of the European Research Executive Agency (REA) named ‘TransEET’ (Transforming Education with Emerging Technologies - Project No: 101078875). The content of this study reflects the views only of the authors.

References

- Grizioti, M., & Kynigos, C. (2023). Integrating Computational Thinking and data science: the case of modding classification games. *Informatics in Education*, 23(1), 101–124 <https://doi.org/10.15388/infedu.2024.03>
- Grizioti, M., & Nikolaou, MS. (2023). Enhancing Student’s 21st Century Skills Through Playing and Modifying Embodied Digital Classification Games. In D. Diamantidis, M. Karavakou, M. Grizioti & C. Kynigos (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Technology in Mathematics Teaching*, (pp. 61–68). Athens, Greece. NKUA.
- Kynigos, C. (2008) Black-and-white-box perspectives to distributed control and constructionism in learning with robotics. *Workshop. Proceedings of SIMPAR 2008, Intl. Conf. on Simulation, Modeling and Programming for Autonomous Robots*, pp. 1–9.
- Nikolaou, MS. (2022). Design and development of a digital kinesthetic game to support embodied learning of classification skills. *Master’s Thesis Dissertation*, University of West Attica.
- Sharma, R., Lajoie, S. P., & Dubé, A. K. (2022). Game Design for Mathematics Education. *Mathematics Education: Research and Innovations*, 25–37. APH Publishing Corporation.
- Simon, L. M., & Cox, D. C. (2019). The role of prototyping in mathematical design thinking. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 56, 100724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmathb.2019.100724>